

extreme earliness of Hokkaido cultivars depends on extremely weak photoperiod sensitivity.

We analyzed the genetic factors controlling the weak photoperiod sensitivity of Hokkaido cultivars by comparing the gene constitution and degree of photoperiod sensitivity of photoperiod-insensitive Norin 20 with those of several other cultivars.

A scatter diagram was constructed for 26 Hokkaido varieties according to basic vegetative growth (BVG) and photoperiod sensitivity (PS) (see figure). BVG was expressed as days to heading under short daylength (10 h) condition, and PS was expressed as the difference between days to heading under whole daylength minus days to heading under short daylength. The cultivars could easily be classified into three groups based on PS: group I (PS < 3.0), group II (4.0 < PS < 10.0), and group III (PS > 20.0). The PS of Norin 20 was 0.6, confirming that this variety has completely lost photoperiod sensitivity (Vergara and Chang 1985).

We compared the gene constitution between Norin 20 (group I) and varieties randomly chosen from groups II and III. Seven varieties were crossed with 10 tester lines to study four photoperiod sensitivity loci: E_1 , E_2 , E_3 , and $Se1$. The dominant alleles of E_1 and $Se1$ loci (E_1 and $Se1^a$ ($Se1^a$)) remarkably improved the photoperiod sensitivity of rice (Okumoto et al 1991), but the effects of those of E_2 and E_3 loci are small (Yamagata et al 1986). (See table for the results of the gene analysis.) For the E_1 locus, all of the varieties examined carry e_1 , an allele for photoperiod

Estimated genotypes for heading-time loci E_1 , E_2 , E_3 , and $Se1$ and degree of photoperiod sensitivity* of seven Hokkaido varieties.

Hokkaido variety	Genotype ^b				Photoperiod sensitivity
	E_1	E_2	E_3	$Se1$	
Norin 20	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^cSe1^c$	0.6
Kitahikari	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^cSe1^c$	6.8
Yukara	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	21.0
Kirara 397	e_1e_1	E_2E_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	8.0
Shlokari	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	E_3E_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	5.3
Elko	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	23.3
Sasahonami	e_1e_1	E_2E_2	E_3E_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	5.3

*See Fig. 1. ^b E_1 , E_2 , E_3 , and $Se1^a$ = photoperiod-sensitive alleles. e_1 , e_2 , e_3 , and $Se1^c$ = photoperiod-insensitive alleles.

Scatter diagram of 26 Hokkaido varieties according to basic vegetative growth and photoperiod sensitivity.

*Days to heading under whole-day length - (days to heading under short-day length [10 h]). ^bDays to heading under short-day length (10 h).

insensitivity. No alleles for photoperiod sensitivity were found among the varieties for the other loci. Norin 20 carries alleles for photoperiod insensitivity alleles at all the above loci, and its genotype was estimated to be $e_1e_1 e_2e_2 e_3e_3 Se1^cSe1^c$. This suggests that the photoperiod insensitivity of Norin 20 can be attributed to the combining effect of these four alleles. However, the cultivars of the same genotype for four loci existed even in Groups II (Kitahikari, PS = 6.8) and III (Yukara, PS = 21.0).

We conclude that e_1 is an essential gene for cultivating rice in Hokkaido. The combining effect of e_1 with an allele(s) for photoperiod insensitivity—but not at E_2 , E_3 , and $Se1$ loci—controls the weak photoperiod sensitivity of Hokkaido varieties.

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QTL analysis of rice seedling vigor in japonica and indica genetic backgrounds

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Breeding for enhanced seedling vigor—a plant's ability to emerge rapidly from soil or water (Heydecker 1960)—continues to be a major challenge for rice breeders in both tropical (Herdt 1991) and temperate (McKenzie et al 1994) rice-growing countries. Vigorous varieties are needed for optimum stand establishment under direct seeded rice cultures. The development of molecular marker maps in rice (McCouch et al 1988) makes it possible to identify and locate genetic factors or quantitative trait loci (QTLs) controlling polygenic characters.

Rice seedling vigor is associated with shoot and root lengths under water-seeded rice culture (Jones and Peterson 1976) and coleoptile and mesocotyl lengths under drill seeding (Turner et al 1982). To identify and locate QTLs underlying these characters, two high-vigor cultivars, indica Black Gora (BG) and temperate japonica Italica Livorno (IL), were crossed to the same maternal parent, Labelle (LBL), a low-vigor tropical japonica. Two molecular maps were constructed based on 204 F_2 plants and 117 restriction fragment length polymorphisms (RFLPs) in LBL/BG and on 118 F_2 plants and 129 random amplified polymorphic DNAs (RAPDs) and 18 RFLPs in LBL/IL.

The LBL/BG map spanned 1496 Haldane cM, with an average marker spacing of 14 cM. Linkage analysis was performed using Mapmaker 3.0 (Lander et al 1987). Total length of the LL/IL map was

1168 cM with an average interval length of 9 cM.

Lengths of shoot, root, coleoptile, and mesocotyl were scored on 172 F₃ families in LBL/BG using replicated slantboard tests at two temperatures (18 and 25 °C) and on 113 F₃ families in LBL/IL at 18 °C. The slantboard test (Jones and Peterson 1976) is a standard laboratory procedure used for screening seedling vigor in California. Interval mapping (LOD = 2.5) using Mapmaker and single-point analyses (P < 0.05) using SAS programs (SAS Institute, 1989) identified 13 QTLs in LBL/BG, including four for shoot length, two each for root and coleoptile lengths, and five for mesocotyl length (see table). Three of these QTLs were expressed at both screening temperatures. In LBL/IL, 12 QTLs were identified including two for coleoptile length and five each for root and mesocotyl lengths (see table).

Most QTLs, including those detected from the common maternal parent, mapped to different rice chromosomes in the two crosses. These results suggest that both genetic background and screening environment may influence QTL expression for seedling vigor. Different sets

of alleles conferring increased seedling vigor may be present in high-vigor indica and japonica genetic donors. The indica BG contributed QTLs with only minor effects for shoot length, the most important determinant of seedling vigor in California's water-seeded rice culture. However, an allele from the temperate japonica cultivar IL accounting for 18.5% of the shoot length variation was identified by single-point analysis. Positive alleles at QTLs identified in the two populations may be useful for seedling vigor enhancement of both japonica and indica cultivars.

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Chromosomal locations of QTLs for length of shoot, root, coleoptile, and mesocotyl measured in slantboard tests in the Labelle/Black Gora and Labelle/Italica Livorno populations as determined by interval and single-factor analysis.

Chromosome no.	Vigor trait	Temp (°C)	Labelle/Black Gora		Labelle/Italica Livorno	
			% variance explained	Nearest marker	% variance explained	Nearest marker
1	Shoot	18, 25	7 ^a	RG536	-	-
	Root	18, 25	31 ^a	RG222	-	-
	Mesocotyl	25	13	RG811	-	-
2	Root	18	9	CD0718	-	-
	Shoot	18, 25	16 ^a	RZ452	18 ^b	OPAD13 ₇₂₀
3	Coleoptile	25	25	RZ448	-	-
	Mesocotyl	18, 25	10	RZ448	-	-
	Shoot	18	8 ^a	RG435	-	-
5	Root	18	-	-	11	OPAJ20 ₁₁₄₀
	Mesocotyl	25	13	RZ67	-	-
	Shoot	18	-	-	50	OPH19 ₁₃₄₀
6	Coleoptile	25	15 ^a	RG716	-	-
	Mesocotyl	18	-	-	14	OPX17 ₁₇₀₀
7	Root	18	-	-	16 ^a	OPY6 ₁₁₅₀
	Mesocotyl	18	-	-	13	RG678
	Shoot	25	28	RZ395	-	-
9	Shoot	18	10 ^a	RZ422	-	-
	Root	18	-	-	11 ^a	OPAA1 ₆₄₀
10	Root	18	-	-	14	OPX2 ₇₀₀
	Coleoptile	18	-	-	21	OPZ12 ₂₄₀₀
11	Coleoptile	18	-	-	13 ^a	OPAN15 ₁₀₅₀
	Mesocotyl	18	-	-	11 ^a	RZ536
12	Mesocotyl	18	-	-	11 ^a	RZ536
	Root	18	-	-	9 ^a	RG341

^aLabelle has the positive allele. ^bBy single-factor analysis.

RFLP mapping of QTLs for yield and other related characters in rice

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Two F₂ populations were established from two indica/indica combinations: Tesanai 2/CB (TSA/CB) and Waiyin 2/CB (WY/CB). CB, from California, USA, was the common male parent. Tesanai 2, from Guangdong, China, is a high-yielding variety noted for its large panicles. Waiyin 2, from IRRI, has large grains. Seventy-three percent of 167 RFLP markers tested revealed polymorphisms between the parents of the two crosses. For each F₂ population, genotypes were determined for 171 plants with 93 RFLP markers in TSA/CB and 101 in WY/CB, respectively. Two linkage maps, made up of 89 marker loci and 93 marker loci of 12 linkage groups, were constructed, respectively, using Mapmaker (Lander et al 1987).

Each of eight characters were subjected to QTL mapping with both ANOVA (SAS Institute Inc. 1988) and interval mapping procedure (Lander and Botstein 1989). In TSA/CB, 22 QTLs for the eight characters were detected by one-way ANOVA (data not shown). The same QTLs were also detected by interval analysis (Table 1). In WY/CB, 19 QTLs for six traits were detected by one-way ANOVA, and, again,